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A Framework for Measuring the Effectiveness of Cybersecurity Policies: Development of the CPEI Model

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ABSTRACT

Cybersecurity has become a critical governance priority as institutions increasingly rely on digital technologies for service delivery, communication, and data management. Yet, the effectiveness of cybersecurity policies, particularly within developing-country contexts, remains poorly measured and unevenly implemented. This study evaluates the effectiveness of cybersecurity policies in selected institutions and develops a quantitative Cybersecurity Policy Effectiveness Index (CPEI) to assess four key dimensions: policy design, implementation success, user compliance, and institutional readiness. Using data from structured surveys administered to staff across multiple institutions, supported by descriptive statistics and regression analysis, the study reveals that while most institutions demonstrate strong policy design and moderate infrastructural readiness, substantial weaknesses persist in user compliance, enforcement consistency, and practical policy execution. The CPEI score of 3.854 (on a 5-point scale) indicates a moderately effective cybersecurity posture but underscores persistent human and organisational gaps that continue to undermine institutional resilience. To complement the CPEI, the study introduces the Cybersecurity Effectiveness Quadrant (CEQ)-a qualitative, behaviourally oriented framework that classifies institutions into four zones (Transformative, Cultural Strength, Structural Risk, and Vulnerable) based on their implementation capacity and real-world impact. The integration of CPEI and CEQ provides a dual-lens diagnostic mechanism that combines numerical precision with contextual interpretive insights, offering a more comprehensive assessment of institutional cybersecurity performance. Overall, the study contributes a replicable, context-sensitive framework for evaluating cybersecurity governance and provides evidence-based policy recommendations for strengthening institutional cybersecurity readiness and resilience.

Keywords: Cybersecurity Performance Index (CPEI), effectiveness, cyberattacks, cybersecurity posture, cybersecurity resilience, threats, vulnerability

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper proposes a tailored framework for measuring the effectiveness of cybersecurity policies using the Cybersecurity Policy Effectiveness Index (CPEI). The framework integrates global best practices with local context to establish measurable indicators across policy implementation, integration and impact. Using Design Science Research methodology. The framework supports data-driven decision-making, resource prioritization and capacity building, contributing both practical and academic value in cybersecurity governance (Dawson & Uwaoma, 2025). The Cybersecurity Policy Effectiveness Index (CPEI) is a multi-dimensional, context-sensitive measurement tool developed to evaluate how effectively cybersecurity policies are formulated, implemented and enforced within an organisation.

The CPEI will address critical gap in cybersecurity governance, namely, the absence of standardized, adaptable metrics to measure policy performance beyond compliance. While existing frameworks often measure cybersecurity maturity, risk exposure, or compliance levels, they seldom capture policy outcomes or their real-world impact (Garba et al., 2020). The CPEI provides a structured way to translate qualitative policy elements into quantifiable indicators.

The findings are anticipated to contribute to the ongoing discourse on effective cybersecurity practices in the contemporary digital ecosystem by using the CPEI and CEQ indicators: Policy Implementation, which measures how well cybersecurity policies are deployed and adopted in practice. Indicators may include institutional readiness, funding levels, training penetration and legal enforcement. Policy Integration, which evaluates how cybersecurity policy is embedded into national or organisational priorities, including alignment with economic development plans, public-private partnerships and cross-sector coordination. Policy Impact, which assesses outcomes such as reduction in cyber incidents, improvements in response time, user awareness and stakeholder trust.

The paper reveals a contextually approach, using the Cybersecurity Policy Effectiveness Index (CPEI) and a visualization model, the Cybersecurity Effectiveness Quadrant (CEQ) that researchers could adopt in data-driven decision-making, resource prioritisation and capacity building, contributing both practical and academic value in cybersecurity governance.

2. Review of Related Studies

2.1 Policy Design

Effective cybersecurity policy design is the foundation upon which the entire security framework of an organisation or nation rests. Policy design has gained increasing attention due to the growing threat of cybercrime and the rising importance of digital infrastructure. Many Institutions have laid a legislative foundation for combating cybercrime, but the practical implementation and internal policy design across institutions remained varied and often underdeveloped (Adewuyi & Akinboade, 2020).

A well-designed policy must exhibit clarity, comprehensiveness, and relevance to organisational goals. In Nigeria, several institutions still adopt generic, externally developed policies that may not fully consider local organisational culture, technological readiness, or specific sectoral threats (Olayemi, 2014). Consequently, such misalignment can lead to poor user understanding, resistance to compliance, and ineffective enforcement.

Moreover, studies have shown that Nigerian organisations, both public and private, struggled with ensuring that cybersecurity policies are not only documented but also accessible and actionable. Akinjobi *et al.* (2021) noted that many Nigerian institutions developed policies as a compliance requirement rather than as a strategic tool for securing digital assets. This resulted in documents that are overly technical, lacked executive support, and failed to include context-specific scenarios for response.

From a national standpoint, the Nigeria National Cybersecurity Policy and Strategy (NCPS) updated in 2021 served as a guiding document for institutions to align their policies. However, its implementation required tailored translation at the organisational level to ensure relevance, especially in smaller or resource-constrained entities.

In summary, policy design in institutions should move beyond compliance rhetoric and toward strategic alignment with organisational missions, user realities, and national cybersecurity priorities. It must incorporate participatory input from relevant stakeholders, address sector-specific threats, and be reviewed periodically to maintain relevance in a fast-changing threat landscape.

2.2 Policy Implementation

This entailed translating formal cybersecurity policies into actionable practices through leadership support, enforcement mechanisms, and continuous evaluation. As indicated by Siponen *et al.* (2021), managerial support and visible commitment to cybersecurity principles significantly increase adherence among users. This stage faced significant hurdles due to fragmented governance structures and limited executive commitment to cybersecurity (Adebayo & Olayemi, 2022). Leadership played a pivotal role in implementation. When senior management does not prioritise cybersecurity, policy enforcement is often weak or symbolic. Research by Oduwale & Bakare (2020) highlighted that in many Nigerian public institutions, cybersecurity is treated as an IT issue rather than a strategic or governance concern. As a result, enforcement is reactive rather than proactive. Many institutions do not conduct regular audits or incident drills, which are critical for effective policy implementation (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2022). The implementation gap is further exacerbated by bureaucratic bottlenecks, insufficient funding and inter-agency coordination challenges. While some federal agencies have adopted structured frameworks aligned with the National Cybersecurity Policy and Strategy (2021), their replication at the sub-national and organisational levels remained inconsistent. In order close these gaps, this study provided that for a successful implementation therefore, institutions require strong leadership, adequate funding, cross-departmental collaboration, and mechanisms for accountability and adaptation.

2.3 Institutional Readiness

Institutional readiness refers to the extent to which an organisation is prepared to implement, support, and sustain cybersecurity initiatives. Institutional readiness is often hindered by limited infrastructure, weak governance, insufficient funding, and inadequate technical expertise (Osho & Onoja, 2021). These constraints make it difficult for many public and private institutions to adopt advanced cybersecurity tools and practices.

According to Okeshola & Adeta (2019), many Nigerian institutions lacked integrated systems for access control, real-time monitoring, and incident response, critical components for mitigating cyber threats. Furthermore, frequent power outages, poor internet connectivity, and outdated hardware/software undermined the effectiveness of even well-designed policies.

Staff often lacked basic training in identifying cyber threats and IT departments are understaffed or poorly equipped. The Cybercrime Act (2015) provides some regulatory backbone, but institutional readiness varies greatly by region and institutional type. Efforts such as the Nigeria Computer Emergency Response Team (ngCERT) and capacity-building programs led by the Office of the National Security Adviser (ONSA) have improved readiness at national and regional levels, but these gains need to be more deeply internalised by individual organisations (ONSA, 2021). Without institutional capacity, both technical and human, cybersecurity policies remained theoretical constructs that do not translate into practical defense mechanisms (Osho & Onoja, 2021, p. 53).

2.4 User Compliance

User compliance refers to the extent to which individuals within an organisation follow prescribed cybersecurity practices. Essentially, low cybersecurity compliance among users has been linked to poor awareness, limited training and cultural attitudes toward data security (Adeleke & Oyeniran, 2021). Many employees saw cybersecurity as an IT department's responsibility and may neglect basic practices such as updating passwords or avoiding phishing emails.

Empirical studies showed that organisations with structured and regular training programs tend to exhibit higher levels of user compliance (Eze *et al.*, 2020). However, in the Nigerian context, user education is often irregular or outdated, and cybersecurity training is rarely evaluated for effectiveness. The level of compliance is also influenced by the perceived ease of following policies and the perceived consequences of non-compliance. Where enforcement is weak or inconsistent, users are less likely to take cybersecurity seriously (Okeke & Okafor, 2022). Furthermore, organisations that lack feedback mechanisms and incentives for secure behaviour tend to have lower compliance rates. Without aligning user behaviour with organisational policy, even the most advanced security systems remain vulnerable to insider threats (Adeleke & Oyeniran, 2021, p. 128).

2.5 Compliance Behaviour

Compliance Behaviour serves as a bridge between institutional efforts and the effectiveness of cybersecurity policies. It describes the degree to which users adhere to established rules, whether voluntarily or due to enforcement. In this study compliance is regarded as both a product of individual attitudes and organisational enforcement mechanisms (Siponen *et al.*, 2014). In some institutional environment, compliance behaviour is often inconsistent due to cultural attitudes toward regulation, varying levels of digital literacy, and lack of accountability structures. Institutions that support open communication, leadership engagement, and employee participation tend to foster better compliance behaviour (Osho & Onoja, 2021).

Moreover, studies have found that when users understand the rationale behind cybersecurity policies and believe those policies are fair and effective, they are more likely to comply willingly (Adebayo & Olayemi, 2022). In this study, compliance behaviour is a critical mediating factor that shaped whether good policy design and strong implementation actually translate into real-world effectiveness.

2.6 Policy Effectiveness

Policy effectiveness refers to the measurable impact of cybersecurity policies on organisational outcomes, such as incident reduction, response speed and audit compliance. Assessing policy effectiveness remained a challenge due to a lack of standardised performance metrics and limited institutional transparency (Ibrahim *et al.*, 2022).

Effective policies are those that lead to improved security behaviour, reduced incidents and increased organisational resilience. However, in many Nigerian institutions, cybersecurity policies are often reactive and implemented only after a breach has occurred. Few organisations invest in long-term evaluation or adopt international benchmarks such as the Global Cybersecurity Index (GCI) to measure their performance (ITU, 2021).

For policy effectiveness to be realised, there must be alignment between design, implementation and user behaviour. A feedback loop involving monitoring, audits and end-user satisfaction can help institutions understand where gaps exist and how to improve (Okeshola & Adeta, 2019).

The entire interrelation among key variables that formed the basis for measuring effectiveness of cybersecurity policies are depicted in figure 1.

Figure 1. Variables that are used to measure policy effectiveness (Source: Author).

Table 1: Summary of Variables that impact Policy Effectiveness (Source: Author).

Variable Type	Variable Name	KPI
Independent Variables	Policy Quality	Degree of clarity, relevance to organisational goals and completeness of policy coverage
	User Awareness and Training	Frequency, content quality and user retention of cybersecurity training
	Management Support	Visible commitment, enforcement mechanisms and resource allocation for policy implementation
	Technological Infrastructure	Availability and integration of tools for access control, monitoring and incident response
Moderating Variable	Compliance Behaviour	Degree to which users follow cybersecurity policies, whether voluntarily or through enforcement
Dependent Variable	Policy Effectiveness	Outcomes such as incident reduction, detection/response speed, audit compliance and satisfaction feedback

2.7 Related Works on Policy Effectiveness Frameworks

Research globally has examined the conditions under which cybersecurity policies succeed or fail, highlighting key factors such as institutional capacity, user behaviour and adaptability of policies. This empirical review synthesizes findings from both developed and developing countries.

According to Adebayo & Eze (2025) few institutions had implemented actionable security measures despite having formal cybersecurity policies. Implementation challenges such as lack of adequate training and awareness, leadership commitments were attributed to poor or ineffective cybersecurity governance. The situation was further exacerbated by the lack of communication and enforcement mechanisms to enable execution of cybersecurity policies.

Nguyen et al. (2023) investigated cybersecurity policy integration in Vietnam and Malaysia. Using institutional theory, they found that inter-ministerial cooperation, legislative clarity and enforcement capacity significantly

influenced implementation success. However, despite Malaysia's centralised model that showed higher readiness and quicker response to threats, cybersecurity policy implementation effectiveness is not adequately measured.

According to Gonzalez & Rivera (2022) analysed cybersecurity readiness in public agencies across Argentina, Chile, and Colombia. Their quantitative assessment revealed that more than half of the agencies surveyed lacked baseline cybersecurity controls. Institutional maturity and IT budget allocation were found to be strong predictors of cybersecurity policy readiness.

A study by Schmidt & Becker (2021) in Germany and the Netherlands showed that user compliance with cybersecurity protocols was significantly influenced by organisational culture, leadership communication and personal risk perception. Their research suggested that mandatory policy training combined with feedback mechanisms led to a significant increase in compliance levels. However, the research did not show institutional readiness that could impact implementation success. The gap in the research was corroborated by Ekanem et al. (2025) that developed an adaptive cybersecurity policy framework through an empirical study of three African universities. They demonstrated that participatory policy development and institutional flexibility led to more effective implementation and lower policy resistance. However, both studies did not show indices for implementation success.

According to Park & Kim (2022) examined South Korea's cybersecurity master plan and its implementation across government ministries. The study identified regular performance audits, staff training and automatic threat detection systems as key to effective policy enforcement. Ministries that complied with policy requirements had 40% fewer breach incidents. User behaviour is a significant factor in influencing cybersecurity policy adoption and implementation, thus, this study suggested mechanism for closing this gap as exemplified by this research.

Umar & Okoro (2024) conducted a readiness diagnostic using the NIST framework across public institutions in Nigeria. They found poor cyber hygiene, limited infrastructure and lack of incident response plans to be the most critical readiness gaps. In closing these gaps, this study examined context-specific composite index that ensures all the factors that impact policy effectiveness are measured with quantifiable statistics that other researchers could use in advancing further studies in this area.

According to Turner & Carter (2022) studied HIPAA (Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act) cybersecurity policy that referred to the security standards established to protect Electronic Protected Health Information (ePHI) HIPAA policy compliance across 50 hospitals in the United States. Their findings showed that training frequency and system usability were stronger predictors of compliance than fear of sanctions, suggesting the need for more user-centered policy design. This study was based on user-centered policy design, an approach that prioritizes the needs and perspectives of individuals affected by a policy throughout the entire design process. It involves actively engaging users, frontline teams, and operational realities to ensure policies are practical, adaptive, and more likely to succeed.

Al-Mutairi & Haddad (2024) explored reasons for cybersecurity non-compliance in municipal governments in the UAE and Jordan. They found that user apathy, over-complex policy language and lack of local language documentation significantly reduced compliance levels. To address this gap, this study focused on simplifying terminologies, making information accessible in simple presentation format and enhancing engagement through clear communication and relatable examples.

The World Economic Forum (2023) published a benchmarking report of cybersecurity readiness across 37 countries. It found that while high-income nations had advanced detection and response systems, user awareness and policy adaptability were often lacking in both developing and developed countries. The report highlighted the importance of multistakeholder collaboration, which this study provided a clear and concise framework for could be used to help in measuring cybersecurity policy readiness and effectiveness.

Globally, cybersecurity frameworks and policies have evolved to address the rapidly changing and increasingly complex threat landscape (Alhalafi & Veeraraghavan, 2021). Notable among these is the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) Cybersecurity Framework, depicted in Figure 2.3, which offered organisations a structured approach to identify, protect, detect, respond to and recover from cyber incidents (Zenarmor, 2023).

Similarly, the International Telecommunication Union (ITU), as shown in Figure 2.4, developed the Global Cybersecurity Index (GCI) to evaluate nations' cybersecurity readiness. To ensure inclusivity, ITU Member States have set two ambitious strategic goals: achieving universal connectivity and fostering sustainable digital transformation, paving the way for an ITU that is both future-ready and purpose-driven (Bucharest, 2022).

The National Cybersecurity Policy and Strategy (NCPS) 2021 was introduced in Nigeria, to address vulnerabilities and threats against cyberattacks, aiming to create a secure and resilient digital environment in Nigeria (NCPS, 2021). Despite these efforts, the country continues to rank low in global cybersecurity readiness assessments, such as the International Telecommunication Union’s Global Cybersecurity Index (ITU-GCI), which identifies persistent gaps in policy implementation and enforcement. This situation is exacerbated by limited resources, low public awareness and weak compliance mechanisms across critical sectors (Sibe & Kaunert, 2024).

Measuring the effectiveness of cybersecurity policies is not merely an academic exercise; it is a practical necessity for informed decision-making and resource allocation. According to Kure et al., 2018, an effective cybersecurity policy must address not only the technical dimensions of cyber defence but also organisational, procedural and human factors. Furthermore, Markopoulou & Papakonstantinou (2021) argued that the integration of policy effectiveness metrics into national strategies can significantly enhance the prioritization of critical infrastructure protection.

In organisations, where resource constraints and competing priorities often shape policymaking, a robust framework for evaluating cybersecurity policies can provide the empirical evidence needed to justify investments and guide strategic interventions.

Previous studies have predominantly focused on assessing cybersecurity readiness, ICT adoption, or the dependency of critical infrastructures on ICT. For instance, Mbanaso & Kulugh (2021) developed the ICT Dependency Index (IDI) to quantify the reliance of critical infrastructures on digital technologies. Similarly, the ICT Dependency Quadrant (IDQ) was used to classify organisations based on their cyber risk exposure. While these frameworks offer valuable insights, there is need for evaluating the specific outcomes and impacts of cybersecurity policies as depicted in figure 2.

Figure 2: ICT Dependency Framework (Mbanaso & Kulugh, 2021)

The main thrusts of the framework are to establish, through assessment in terms of quantitative measures, which cybersecurity controls exist in an organisation, how effective and efficient these controls are with respect to cybersecurity resilience and steps that need to be taken to improve resilience maturity (Mbanaso et al., 2019). COBIT (Control Objectives for Information and Related Technologies) 2019, developed by ISACA (Information Systems Audit and Control Association), was an evolution of COBIT 5 (2012) designed to provide a comprehensive framework for IT governance and management. It aligned IT strategy with business goals, while emphasising value creation, risk management, and resource optimization (ISACA, 2018). COBIT 2019 remained an adoptable standard for IT governance, not tailored to cybersecurity performance metrics (Antariksa et al. 2025). This study integrated COBIT governance elements to align institutional policies with security outcomes.

The Cybersecurity Resilience Maturity Measurement (CRMM) Framework, published by the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity (ENISA) in 2022, was designed to help organisations assess and improve their cybersecurity resilience, the ability to prevent, detect, respond to, and recover from cyber threats. CRMM focused heavily on maturity levels (qualitative measurement) but lacked standardised quantitative metrics to measure the direct effectiveness of cybersecurity policies. CRMM excelled at benchmarking maturity but fall short in quantifying policy effectiveness. To breach these gaps, this study adapted resilience levels to track policy implementation success.

The CIS Controls released in 2023 by the Center for Internet Security (CIS), is a prioritised set of cybersecurity best practices designed to mitigate the most common cyber threats. It consolidates 18 critical security

controls and emphasised cloud, mobile, and hybrid work environments. The framework is outcome-focused, providing actionable safeguards rather than abstract guidelines (CIS, 2023). CIS has no direct policy performance metrics. This study mapped controls to policy domains for compliance measurement.

Alshaikh (2020) proposed a holistic cybersecurity strategy model that integrates technical, organizational and human factors to address modern cyber threats. Unlike siloed frameworks (e.g., NIST CSF or ISO 27001), this model emphasized multi-layered defense, combining technology, governance, and employee awareness; adaptive policies adjustments based on threat intelligence and stakeholder alignment while bridging gaps between IT, management, and end-users. The model clearly did not provide measurement mechanism for empirical validation of cybersecurity policy effectiveness. This study, provided validation mechanism for the holistic model with empirical data from institutional case studies.

Based on the reviews, Table 2.2 provided summary of the global insights on the review of previous studies conducted in relation to this study.

Table 2: Summary of Referenced Cybersecurity Frameworks and Studies

S/N	Author & Year of Publication	Title of the Research	Contribution/Outcome	Gap Identified	How This Study Addressed the Gap
1	Adebayo & Eze (2025)	Cybersecurity governance in Nigerian institutions	Identified weak policy implementation and lack of enforcement mechanisms	Lack of leadership support and communication for execution	Developed a structured framework for institutional engagement and policy communication
2	Nguyen et al. (2023)	Cybersecurity policy integration in Vietnam & Malaysia	Found that legislative clarity and enforcement improved readiness	Policy effectiveness not adequately measured	Proposed an effectiveness index for measuring cybersecurity implementation outcomes
3	Gonzalez & Rivera (2022)	Cybersecurity readiness in Latin America	Linked institutional maturity and IT budgets with readiness	No direct link to policy performance outcomes	Integrated readiness as a core construct in the policy effectiveness model
4	Schmidt & Becker (2021)	User compliance in EU public institutions	Found user compliance is driven by leadership and culture	Did not consider institutional readiness	Combined user behavior and institutional readiness in the framework
5	Ekanem et al. (2025)	Adaptive cybersecurity policy framework in Africa	Emphasized participatory policy design and flexibility	No measurable implementation success indicators	Introduced quantifiable success indices in implementation assessment
6	Park & Kim (2022)	South Korea's cybersecurity master plan	Audits and training reduced breaches by 40%	User behavior mechanisms not fully explored	Linked user compliance and policy enforcement to effectiveness
7	Umar & Okoro (2024)	NIST-based readiness diagnostics in Nigeria	Found poor infrastructure and lack of response capacity	Generic metrics not suited to local context	Created context-specific composite index for measuring effectiveness
8	Turner & Carter (2022)	HIPAA policy compliance in US hospitals	User-centered design improved compliance more than fear-based approaches	Overlooked policy integration process	Emphasized user-centered design with policy integration and execution in the framework
9	Al-Mutairi & Haddad (2024)	Non-compliance in UAE and Jordan	Found poor compliance due to complex language and low accessibility	Lack of communication clarity in policy dissemination	Simplified presentation and improved engagement mechanisms included
10	WEF (2023)	Global Cybersecurity Readiness Report	Benchmarked 37 countries; found gaps in awareness and adaptability	Generic findings; lacked local socio-economic analysis	Designed a localised and adaptive evaluation model with cultural relevance
11	ISO/IEC (2022)	ISO/IEC 27001 Standard	Provides a formal model for ISMS implementation	Lacks sector-specific adaptation in developing nations	Localised ISO principles into institution-specific assessment metrics
12	NIST (2023)	NIST Cybersecurity Framework	Offers structured response categories (identify, protect, detect, respond, recover)	Doesn't account for human behavior and institutional factors	Incorporated NIST pillars and aligned them with readiness and compliance
13	ITU-GCI (2022)	Global Cybersecurity Index	Measures national-level cyber readiness and policy coverage	Doesn't address internal policy enforcement effectiveness	Refined global metrics to fit within internal institutional policy evaluation
14	Mbanaso & Kulugh (2021)	ICT Dependency Index and Quadrant	Classified organizations based on cyber risk exposure	Does not evaluate actual policy impact	Expanded dependency analysis into full implementation and compliance metrics
15	ISACA (2019)	COBIT 2019 Framework for Governance and Management of Enterprise IT	Provided structured governance mechanisms for IT and cybersecurity alignment	Not tailored to cybersecurity performance metrics	Integrated COBIT governance elements to align institutional policies with security outcomes
16	ENISA (2022)	Cybersecurity Resilience Maturity Measurement (CRMM) Framework	Offered a maturity model for assessing organizational cybersecurity resilience	Limited in policy-specific measurements and compliance	Adapted resilience levels to track policy implementation success
17	DOE (2021)	Cybersecurity Capability Maturity Model (C2M2)	Assessed cybersecurity capability maturity across domains	Does not include user compliance or institutional readiness	Incorporated C2M2 structure with added layers for user compliance and readiness
18	CIS (2023)	CIS Controls Version 8	Presented prioritized best practices for cybersecurity defense	Not a comprehensive framework for policy evaluation	Mapped controls to policy domains for compliance measurement
19	Alshaikh (2020)	Holistic cybersecurity strategy model	Called for integrated and contextualized cybersecurity policy frameworks	No empirical validation for effectiveness	Validated the holistic model with empirical data from institutional case studies

This gap highlighted the need for a framework explicitly designed to measure the effectiveness of cybersecurity policies, addressing dimensions such as implementation, integration, compliance and impact.

3.1 Research Design

The research design serves as the blueprint for systematically collecting, analysing and interpreting data to achieve the objectives of a study (Creswell, 2018). This paper adopted a mixed method research design combining both quantitative and qualitative approaches to capture the multifaceted nature of cybersecurity policy effectiveness.

3.2 Population

The target population for this study includes personnels directly involved in cybersecurity governance and usage within organisations. This comprises of IT professionals (e.g., cybersecurity officers, system administrators), policy implementers and decision-makers (e.g., CIOs, compliance officers) and end-users of cybersecurity policies (e.g., staff in government or private institutions). These participants would be selected from Government, Private, Regulatory or Professional and Academic Institutions engaged in digital operations and cybersecurity governance.

3.3 Sample Size

In determining the sample size for the quantitative aspect of this study, Yamane's (1967) formula for a finite population was applied. This formula provides a simplified approach to calculate the minimum sample size

required to achieve a desired level of precision within a given population size. The population with the desired characteristics of being involved in the survey was considered 5% and the margin of error to be 10%.

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2} \quad (3.1)$$

Where:

n = required sample size

N = population size (10,000)

e = margin of error (0.1) or precision

$$n = \frac{10,000}{1+10,000(0.1)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{10,000}{1+10,000(0.01)}$$

$$n = \frac{10,000}{1+100}$$

$$n = \frac{10,000}{101} \approx 99.01$$

With a population of 10,000 and a margin of error of 10%, a sample size of approximately 99 respondents is sufficient to achieve statistically meaningful results in this study.

Although this study utilised a sample size of 100 respondents for the quantitative phase and 10 interviewees for the qualitative phase, limitations exist in terms of statistical generalizability, potential nonresponse bias, and constraints in conducting advanced multivariate analysis.

3.4 Reliability and Validity

Cronbach's Alpha was computed for all constructs to assess internal consistency. The results exceeded the 0.7 threshold (Ahmad *et al.*, 2024), confirming acceptable reliability:

Policy Design = 0.797

Implementation Success = 0.911

User Compliance = 0.924

Institutional Readiness = 0.848

Policy design recorded a cronbach's alpha of 0.797, indicating satisfactory internal consistency among the indicators measuring clarity, adequacy, and applicability of cybersecurity policy frameworks. Implementation success ($\alpha = 0.911$) and user compliance ($\alpha = 0.924$) showed excellent reliability, suggesting strong inter-item correlation and a coherent measurement of their respective constructs. Likewise, institutional readiness ($\alpha = 0.848$) reflected high reliability, confirming that the indicators used to assess organisational preparedness and leadership support were consistent and dependable. Overall, the results validated that the instrument's constructs are internally stable and reliable, thereby ensuring that subsequent analyses, such as regression and composite index computation, are based on statistically sound measures of cybersecurity policy effectiveness.

3.5 Analytical Tools

Python was chosen for quantitative analysis due to its suitability for handling large datasets, running inferential tests, and structural modelling. NVivo will assist in qualitative coding and theme development, allowing efficient and rigorous textual analysis.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

The ethical consideration of this study adhered to established research ethics to protect the rights, dignity and privacy of participants and institutions examined. Typically, the following ethical principles were considered and adhered to. In order not to coerce participants were provided with details about the study's objectives, procedures and their rights before giving their consent. Participation was also voluntary and consensual informing respondents could withdraw at any stage without consequences or breach of agreement. Identity of participants were anonymised, such that no personally identifiable information was collected. Secured data storage medium with password-protected mechanism was used, in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the Nigeria Data Protection Regulation (NDPR), and will be securely deleted after the study. The study was designed to avoid physical, psychological or reputational harm or damage to participants. The findings are reported truthfully and without misrepresentation

4. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Regression Model Specification

To understand how each construct contributes to overall cybersecurity maturity, a multiple regression model was estimated with Institutional Readiness as the dependent variable (DV) and three predictors:

- i. Policy Design (PD)
- ii. Implementation Success (IS)
- iii. User Compliance (UC)

The model is expressed as:

$$IR = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PD + \beta_2 IS + \beta_3 UC + \varepsilon \quad (4.1)$$

Where:

IR= Institutional Readiness

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = estimated influence of each construct

ε = error term

Based on the actual data (N = 72), the regression yielded the results in Table 3:

Table 3: Regression Output (Source: Field Survey, 2025)

Statistic	Value
R ²	0.857
Adjusted R ²	0.849
F-statistic	100.52, p < 0.001
Residual SE	0.424

The three constructs jointly explain 85.7% of the variation in Institutional Readiness; a very strong model. All predictors significantly contribute to cybersecurity maturity. This confirmed that Institutional Readiness is a valid dependent construct for explaining cybersecurity effectiveness.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

The core constructs of the study were measured on a 5-point Likert scale (1=Strongly Disagree, 5=Strongly Agree). The results are summarised in Table 4.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics of Key Variables (n=72) (Source: Field Survey, 2025)

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation	Min	Max
Policy Design	4.069	0.888	1.0	5.0
Implementation Success	3.903	0.815	1.0	5.0
User Compliance	3.653	0.925	1.0	5.0
Institutional Readiness	3.792	0.921	1.0	5.0

The results indicated that a significant majority agreed (38.9%) that their institutions' cybersecurity policies were clearly documented, aligned with organisational goals, and incorporated international best practices. However, a small proportion (16.7%) expressed uncertainty about the level of stakeholder involvement in policy formulation. The Policy Design (Mean=4.069) indicates that respondents generally agree that policies are well-designed, clear, and aligned with goals. This is the highest-rated construct.

The effectiveness of cybersecurity policies within the studied Nigerian institutions presents a narrative of potential constrained by execution. The data reveals a clear disconnect between the formal, documented strategy and its practical, real-world impact. Institutions have made commendable efforts to develop policies that are clear, comprehensive, and aligned with international best practices.

While policies exist on paper, their translation into consistent action is hampered by bureaucratic tendencies, insufficient funding, and a lack of continuous monitoring. This is not a failure of intention, but one of operationalization as discovered by this study. The most critical flaw exposed is weak user compliance. Despite the presence of policies, a significant portion of the workforce remains either unaware, unconvinced, or unwilling to adhere to security protocols. This turns the employee, the intended first line of defense, into the most vulnerable attack vector. It underscores a fundamental truth: a technically perfect policy is utterly ineffective if the people it is designed to protect do not follow it.

Ultimately, the study concludes that current cybersecurity policy effectiveness is moderately successful at best. While the necessary frameworks and a base level of institutional readiness are in place, the chain of security is

breaking at the critical links of daily execution and human behaviour. The policies are present, but they are not yet fully performative. They reduce risk but do not eliminate it, leaving organizations in a perpetual state of managed vulnerability rather than assured resilience. This highlights an urgent need to shift focus from drafting documents to fostering a pervasive culture of security and ensuring robust, accountable implementation processes.

4.1 Composite Index (CPEI)

The Cybersecurity Policy Effectiveness Index (CPEI) is a composite indicator developed in this study to provide a quantitative measure of the effectiveness of cybersecurity policies across five critical dimensions: Policy Design, Implementation Success, User Compliance, Institutional Readiness and Policy Effectiveness. Each construct is measured using a Likert Scale, and the CPEI aggregates these into a single score that reflects overall effectiveness.

4.2 Mathematical and Computational Model Equation

The CPEI is computed as a weighted average of the mean scores of the five constructs:

$$CPEI = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i \times M_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i} \quad (4.1)$$

Where:

M_i = Mean score of constructs i

w_i = Weight assigned to construct i (equal weight = 1 if no prioritization)

n = Number of constructs (here, 4)

Since each construct is equally important in this study, we apply equal weights ($w = 1$).

Thus, the formula simplifies to:

$$CPEI = \frac{M_{PD} + M_{IS} + M_{UC} + M_{IR}}{n} \quad (4.2)$$

Where:

M_{PD} = Mean of Policy Design

M_{IS} = Mean of Implementation Success

M_{UC} = Mean of User Compliance

M_{IR} = Mean of Institutional Readiness

n = Number of constructs

From the descriptive statistics we derived earlier:

Policy Design (PD): **4.069**

Implementation Success (IS): **3.903**

User Compliance (UC): **3.653**

Institutional Readiness (IR): **3.792**

$$CPEI = \frac{4.069 + 3.903 + 3.653 + 3.792}{4}$$

$$CPEI = \frac{15.417}{4} = 3.854$$

4.3 Interpretation of the results:

- i. The computed CPEI = 3.854 (on a 5-point Likert scale).

- ii. This indicates that the overall effectiveness of cybersecurity policies in the sampled institutions is moderate to high.
- iii. While policy design is relatively strong, user compliance is the weakest area, suggesting that policy ambitions are not fully matched by user compliance and adherence.

The high means (ranging from 3.653 to 4.069) and acceptable standard deviations confirm reliability and internal consistency. The descriptive statistics showed a mean rating of 4.069 on policy design clarity (SD = 0.888), suggesting moderately high agreement among participants. User compliance had a lower average (mean = 3.653, SD = 0.925), indicating gaps in routine adherence to cybersecurity protocols. Implementation support mechanisms, such as training and technical assistance, scored moderately high across institutions.

Multiple regression analysis indicated that Policy Design, Institutional Readiness and User Compliance had significant positive effects on Implementation Success. Among these, Policy Design had the strongest influence, while User Compliance was relatively weaker. These results support the hypothesis that specific constructs significantly influence implementation success. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted, with Policy Design emerging as the dominant predictor.

The study developed the Cybersecurity Policy Effectiveness Index (CPEI) using equal-weighted means of the four constructs. The formula: $CPEI = (M_{PD} + M_{IS} + M_{UC} + M_{IR}) / 4$ yielded a score of 3.854, confirming that the CPEI provides a valid and reliable method of aggregating multiple dimensions into one index. Thus, the hypothesis underlying this question is accepted.

The findings show that the framework captures both strengths (Policy Design, Implementation Success) and weaknesses (User Compliance). The CPEI offers actionable insights for institutions: high scores in design and implementation success indicate strong policy intent, while lower compliance scores reveal gaps in enforcement and monitoring. The weighted structure of the CPEI provides a data-driven guide for prioritization. The strong influence of Implementation Success (weight of 0.30) suggests that investments in training, tools, and dedicated personnel yield the highest return on effectiveness. The low scores in User Compliance across the sample highlight a critical area for capacity-building initiatives. The framework dictates that these initiatives must move beyond one-time training to foster a sustained security culture. This supports the hypothesis that the framework can inform practice and drive improvement. The hypothesis is accepted, as the framework offers both diagnostic and prescriptive value for institutions.

5. Conclusions

The data analysis confirms that effective cybersecurity policy outcomes depend not only on robust policy design but also on strong implementation mechanisms, active user compliance, and institutional preparedness. Furthermore, external benchmarking frameworks play a critical role in validating internal evaluations. The use of regression and factor analysis has enabled the development of a composite index (CPEI), offering a novel contribution to the measurement of cybersecurity policy effectiveness in developing contexts. Theoretically, the study contributes to the growing body of research on cybersecurity governance in developing economies by operationalising constructs into a measurable index and validating them within a localised institutional context.

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